

Unleashing the Potential: Opening up the Nation's Collections

A Report by the Culture is Digital Digitisation
Taskforce

(now the Collections Digitisation Network)

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Authors:

Valerie Johnson; Helen Hardy; Aruna Bhaugeerutty; Paola Marchionni; Jack Butterworth; Andy Appleyard; Susannah Baccardax; Jane Bramwell; Philip Carlisle; Anna De Sousa; Andrew Ellis; Jane Finnis; Kevin Gosling; Kristian Jensen; Harry Kerr; Colette McFadden; Chris Mumby; Elaine O'Shea-Phillips; Sonia Ranade; Tom Scott; Vincent Smith; Fiona Talbott; David Thomas; Ailsa Vigrass.

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Chair's reflection

This report, looking strategically at digitisation at a national level, was originally completed in the first few months of 2020, just before the Covid pandemic and first lockdowns. As priorities shifted to meet this new context, the publication of the report was put into abeyance. However when the group reconvened, it was decided that many of the issues identified in the report remain vitally relevant and that the report still has value.

Some things have moved on, showing that the report came from a moment in time. For example, The Arts and Humanities Research Council-funded *Towards a National Collection* programme has delivered many insights, representing a “major investment using digital technology to create a unified national collection of the UK's museums, libraries, galleries and archives to maintain global leadership in digital humanities and arts research”¹, which very much speaks to the issues discussed in the report.

The rapid and sustained shift to online access during the pandemic only served to emphasise the importance of digitisation, digital access to and digital uses of collections. One issue that has risen up the agenda since the original report was written is shared heritage. Though this is not the place for an in-depth discussion, the Network is aware that digitisation can also play an important role in sharing heritage, particularly internationally, and that this aspect of digitisation also deserves attention. Other issues such as sustainability are of increasing importance and urgency to the sector and to society.

Though the group was initially a time-limited taskforce, members decided to continue and the Collections Digitisation Network now exists in its own right to champion this work and to be a forum for open discussion, collaboration and action around digitisation and digital skills.

Digitisation is a complex issue but is absolutely central to facilitating access to collections and a vital part of research infrastructure. There is a long way to go before the potential we talk about is fully realised, so we therefore present the report as a contribution to continuing action towards 'Unleashing the Potential' held in the UK's extraordinary and uniquely important collections.

Valerie Johnson

Chair of the Culture is Digital Digitisation Taskforce

¹ <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-offer/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/towards-a-national-collection-opening-uk-heritage-to-the-world>

Executive summary

Digitisation has the potential to be extraordinarily transformative, to be the means by which cultural content can be unlocked and made newly accessible. It makes new and surprising content available for new audiences and new uses, preserves some aspects of the original in the event of its loss, and creates data so that cultural content can be re-surfaced and reused in exciting and innovative ways by present and future generations.

Digitisation can enable the linking of collections so that as a whole they are more than the sum of their parts, either as a research infrastructure or for telling bigger stories in a wider context. In addition, authentic digitised collections can play a crucial role in combatting misinformation and providing trusted data and trusted sources. The potential is enormous, and there is therefore an urgent national, societal imperative towards better and greater digitisation. The UK has an opportunity to lead internationally in this space.

In March 2018, the 'Culture is Digital' policy paper was released, recognising that the UK holds some of the world's most significant collections, and the power of digitisation to unlock these, expand the reach of the UK's cultural assets and enable collections to be more than the sum of their parts. The report included a commitment that "The National Archives will work with culture and heritage sector representatives to develop a new strategic approach to the digitisation and presentation of cultural objects, for example, looking at the common standards needed to make our nation's great cultural assets more interoperable, discoverable and sustainable."²

A Digitisation Taskforce was set up for this strategic review, led by The National Archives, with membership from Arts Council England (ACE), BBC, British Film Institute (BFI), British Library, Collections Trust, Culture24, National Lottery Heritage Fund (the Heritage Fund), Jisc, Natural History Museum, Oxford University, Tate and the Wellcome Collection. Further members have joined the ongoing Collections Digitisation Network more recently, and we look forward to its continued growth.

The Taskforce explored the resources currently available around the digitisation of collections, and surveyed a wide range of museums, libraries, galleries and archives to understand the opportunities and barriers. Key findings and recommendations are summarised in this report (originally prepared in 2019-20) whose publication was delayed by the Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent changes. The current Collections Digitisation Network, which has emerged from

² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/culture-is-digital/culture-is-digital>

the original Taskforce group, feel that these findings are still highly relevant and are therefore publishing them despite these delays. Case studies were prepared at the time, and these have been included to provide examples for the six key themes – where these have been updated relevant dates are noted in the text. While standards are a focus of the commitment above, in practice it was other barriers that seem to pose a greater risk to realising the benefits of digitisation and joining up cultural collections. With that in mind, nine priority areas supported by a network-centred approach are recommended.

Recommendations and commitments

The Digitisation Taskforce recommends that:

1. Digital Centres of Excellence are supported

National, larger-scale or relevant specialist collections-holding institutions should be supported to act, formally or informally, as Digital Centres of Excellence to share best practice, skills and equipment with others in the sector.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to act as a focal point and knowledge-sharing network around the subject of cultural heritage digitisation, and share lessons learnt from Digital Centres of Excellence in their own particular disciplines and communities.

2. Resources are found to support Digital Centres of Excellence

Funders, infrastructure initiatives, higher education and strategic partners should consider resource to develop and sustain Digital Centres of Excellence.

The Collections Digitisation Network will bring new innovation partners and non-government funders to the table.

3. Nationally funded programmes focused on interoperability and data-sharing should take account of this report

Nationally-funded programmes focused on interoperability and data-sharing in the cultural and heritage sector, such as The Arts and Humanities Research Council's *Towards a National Collection*, should take account of this report and its recommendations.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to work with UK Research and Innovation, The Arts & Humanities Research Council and others, sharing the work of the Taskforce and inviting collaboration and support.

4. Increased investment, promotion and support for content aggregators

There should be increased investment, publicity and support for sector-approved content aggregators

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to support national, international and sector specific content aggregators that act as major gateways to digitised collections, such as Discovery, Archives Hub, Art UK and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, promoting them to their communities.

5. Improved dissemination of standards

There should be improved dissemination of standards through the provision of a Digital Resources Portal, and knowledge sharing via the Digital Centres of Excellence.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to contribute to the development of approaches on persistent identifiers, for example the project undertaken by the Towards a National Collection programme.

6. Economic valuation models for collections and collections data should be developed

Economic valuation models for collections and collections data should be developed. The Department for Digital, Culture Media and Sport should support further study in this area.

The Collections Digitisation Network will provide case studies and share research to illustrate collections value, impact and best practice.

7. The digital skills and maturity of the cultural sector should be developed

The digital skills and maturity of the cultural sector should be developed, for example through Art Council England's Digital Culture Network and Digital Maturity Index, and the National Lottery Heritage Fund's Digital Skills for Heritage initiative.

The Collections Digitisation Network will provide mentoring, skills sharing, and workshops, subject to resources.

8. Funders should be encouraged to include preservation and sustainability within their requirements

Funders such as The Arts and Humanities Research Council and National Heritage Lottery Fund should consider including preservation and sustainability within their requirements.

The Collections Digitisation Network will support the production of guiding principles for digital preservation.

9. Investment and research into long-term data infrastructure should be maximised

Link existing initiatives to maximise investment and research into sustainable long-term data infrastructure.

The Collections Digitisation Network will collaborate with UK Research and Innovation and The Arts and Humanities Research Council initiatives, such as Infrastructure roadmaps and Towards a National Collection, and new areas of action when these arise.

Introduction

This report describes the work and findings of the Digitisation Taskforce, which formed in response to the Culture is Digital project and its progress report published in June 2019.

What does the sector mean by digitisation?

The objective of the Taskforce was to take a strategic view of digitisation: to identify challenges and opportunities, and to suggest ways to address both. There is, however, no single definition of what is meant by digitisation in the context of cultural collections. Using facilitated discussion, presentations and workshops, the group surfaced and explored the main issues, creating a wider survey to gather insights from cultural and heritage institutions about how they define and approach digitisation, and their primary challenges.

In January 2019, the taskforce ran a digitisation survey³. The results of the survey showed that, at its core, digitisation is a combination of releasing digital data about collections and creating digital representations of analogue or physical objects. Almost all the survey respondents saw digitisation in terms of digital representations of their collection, for example, scans, photographs, 3D representations and digital film formats. Over 50% also included 'catalogue' or inventory data – for instance data fields describing an object, including provenance data such as where and when it was collected. The Taskforce, and this report, focuses on collections that have been or could be digitised, rather than those 'born digital', although there is recognised to be a degree of overlap in areas such as digital preservation.

As well as being subject to a wide variety of definitions and nuances for different collection types, digitisation is not a singular process, but a set of stages, for example, pre- or post- digitisation preparation; 2D or 3D image capture and processing; format conversion; data capture and enhancement such as geo-referencing; and data publication, ideally supporting wider aggregation and interoperability. These stages in turn are often part of a wider programme, which may include funding bids and business case development; policy development and standards; infrastructural requirements and technical support; data storage and digital preservation; as well as models for licensing or charging.

³ Ibbotson, M., & Steffens-Dyke, T. (2024, July 23). Culture is Digital Survey Findings and Segmentation 2019. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12799185>

Digitisation in the cultural heritage sector

Map showing distribution of responses to our digitisation survey.

Responses to our survey covered a good regional distribution of cultural institutions across England. Over a quarter of institutions were based in London, but away from the South-East, responses were quite evenly spread out across the country (see map).

Institutions that we surveyed felt that almost three-quarters of their collections could be digitised, although only around 18% are described as digitised at present. The variety of UK collections must also be remembered – from papers, books and diaries, to audio-visual, artworks, objects of all sorts, natural specimens, and derived materials such as analyses. They are also preserved or held in a huge variety of ways, taking into account physical storage such as cabinets;

environmental conditions such as temperature; and different media of preservation. And their potential audiences are huge, with great diversity of needs and wants; from local to global; scientists to schools, public citizens and beyond.

Across this complex landscape, taking the survey alongside the workshops and discussions, six key themes emerged and are explored in the next section:

1. Taking a strategic view of content
2. Discovery and data interoperability
3. Standards
4. Funding digitisation
5. Supporting skills
6. Preservation and sustainability

These themes are closely linked and need to work together for maximum impact.

Theme 1: Taking a strategic view of content

Image of Carl Linnaeus made out of digitised specimen images (and a close up of his eye) © The Trustees of the Natural History Museum.

All the institutions that we surveyed or spoke to said that their top reason for digitisation was access to their collections, with digital data increasing the potential for remote access; wider access, and new forms of access, in line with their overall mission or duty.

In the UK, many museums and cultural destinations are free to the public, and in keeping with this ethos almost three-quarters

of institutions provide free access to their collection catalogues or digital assets. However, we also discovered that 1 in 5 institutions did not publish any digitised material. There were a variety of reasons behind this – not only lack of resource; but issues around sensitivity, skills, systems, and target audiences (for example, where material is only made available on request to researchers). This digitised but unpublished material represents a significant opportunity to enhance UK digital collections, if its release can be facilitated.

Yet despite this aspiration and potential, fewer than half the institutions surveyed have any digitisation policy or strategy. Digitisation is often more responsive than strategic, even within ongoing digitisation programmes in larger collections, and particularly where institutions are responding to project-based funding from funding bodies. This leaves a current landscape of digitised content that is fragmented and patchy, with strengths around certain themes, but also gaps. It was noted that in general there is less freely accessible 20th century material, due to copyright restrictions, and a lower representation of digitised non-Western content.

Case study: Wellcome Collection digitisation

Digitisation in process at Wellcome Collection by Thomas S.G. Farnetti. Wellcome Collection CC-BY.

Wellcome Collection is Wellcome's free museum and library. Our goal is to challenge how we think and feel about health by connecting medicine, health and art.

To further our aim to increase engagement with our collections for as wide and diverse a group of people as possible we have, to date, digitised and made freely available nearly 300,000 items, comprising 43 million images.

Although technology and systems greatly help us optimise our workflows, our success in managing large-scale digitisation is largely down to the team. We subscribe to the "self-organising" principle of team management. Within a framework of collaborative quarterly objective-setting and clarity on constraints, teams can experiment with different approaches to how they work.

We treat our digitisation efforts as "pipelines" rather than discrete projects. A pipeline consists of a continuous workflow focused on specific formats or content types. This continuity helps us make efficient use of staff availability and expertise, equipment, contractual relationships, space, etc. The team is encouraged to innovate with continuous improvement as a key performance indicator.

We've automated our ingest workflows using open source digitisation workflow systems. Automation reduces unnecessary manual labour and improves workflow management, increasing the number of items we can handle at any given time.

Storage and system scalability are a serious consideration when digitising at scale. We have moved all our digital assets and workflow systems from local servers to Amazon Web Services (AWS), and have found this to be cost-effective, more robust and allows us to provide standards-based services such as BagIt for file fixity, development of open source services, and replication to multiple locations.

We have realised major benefits from transforming our ways of working. The key has been directing our focus on developing cross-functional teams that are

empowered to organise and act, working across flexible pipelines of work, and the integration and development of open source software as part of our drive to automate and transition to Cloud storage.

Case study: Plugged In, Powered Up

In 2019, The National Archives launched a strategy and range of programmes designed to build capacity in the archives sector. This focuses on improving digital engagement, access and content preservation by the sector but this is underpinned by broader work on underlying digital skills.

Our wide-ranging 2019 survey carried out with Jisc revealed wide disparities in technical skill and capacity between organisations and within them. This means that the programmes needed to cover multiple topics, be pitched at different skill levels and be suitable for different types and sizes of organisation.

The programmes developed fall on a spectrum, from less structured sharing of best practice through meetings of the Digital Archives Learning Exchange (DALE) and peer mentoring of inexperienced digital practitioners by more experienced colleagues elsewhere in the sector; to structured digital preservation training delivered in person at Kew ('Archives School') or online ('Novice to Ninja', developed with the Digital Preservation Coalition). More formal educational models also form part of the programme with a PGCert in Computing for Cultural Heritage being piloted with the British Library and Birkbeck, University of London and the continuation of The National Archives 'Bridging the Digital Gap' program to bring trainees with non-traditional and technical backgrounds into archives.

No single intervention from these strands would be sufficient to meet the sector's significant need but evaluating them will help show which interventions are most appropriate for organisations with low to high digital capacity and low to high capacity in general. The objective is to bring good practice into many different parts of the sector at once.

What could a strategic approach look like?

A single strategic approach to UK cultural heritage digitisation is unlikely to be feasible, or to be able fully to represent the diversity of collections, digitisation approaches and potential audiences. The group did consider a thematic gap analysis of collections currently digitised, but concluded that this would be premature as there is currently 'more gap than content', given the relatively low percentage of material digitised.

In addition, there is currently no means to find out consistently what has already been digitised. With that in mind, the group were aware of and applauded initiatives such as the Arts and Humanities Research Council funded network, led by University of Glasgow, for a global dataset of digitised texts⁴, and the British Library's Global Register of Digitised Content.

Instead of a single, overarching strategy, therefore, the Taskforce explored the concept of strategic networks and Centres of Excellence, that could provide both a strategic overview function, a means of sharing best practice and supporting capabilities. Institutions such as The National Archives, British Film Institute, Natural History Museum, British Library and Art UK already operate in many respects as centres of excellence, with subject-matter expertise in their collections and in related digitisation. This model could be extended if resources were available.

It is likely that these national Centres could form a matrix, taking into account subject matter; technology provision (for example, shared services or expertise in digital storage and preservation); and geographic coverage. A national hub might, for instance, work with regional museums and archives or with related sectors such as Higher Education to reach more local collections. It might train others and share best practice, or actively provide digitisation equipment and services, depending on resources and needs.

Recommendations

Recommendation 1:

National, larger-scale or relevant specialist collections-holding institutions should be supported to act, formally or informally, as Digital Centres of Excellence to share best practice, skills and equipment with others in the sector.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to act as a focal point and knowledge-sharing network around the subject of cultural heritage digitisation, and share lessons learnt from Digital Centres of Excellence in their own particular disciplines and communities.

Recommendation 2:

Funders, infrastructure initiatives, higher education and strategic partners should consider resource to develop and sustain Digital Centres of Excellence.

The Collections Digitisation Network will bring new innovation partners and non-government funders to the table.

⁴ <https://gddnetwork.arts.gla.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/GDDNetworkFinalReport-2.pdf>

Theme 2: Discovery and data interoperability

Content in cultural collections is engaging and insightful – however, much of it is undiscovered. The true value of the UK’s collections is locked away and audiences are poorly served. Even with digitised collections, particularly across UK collections, there is often no easy way to search (by subject, person or place) in order to assist with personal interest, academic study, commercial or scholarly research.

Mapping digitised cultural collections in the UK

Complementary to the digitisation taskforce survey, DCMS commissioned a feasibility study to look at a recommended framework for mapping and connecting digitised cultural collections within England.⁵ The aim was to better understand the application of emerging technologies in making collections searchable across institutions. This study was undertaken by The Collections Trust, a member of the Taskforce, in collaboration with Knowledge Integration.

The study successfully built and demonstrated a test aggregator that could ingest data from a range of institutions using various technical means, and without the institutions having to format their contributions to any kind of set template. The potential and pitfalls of agreed emerging technologies were demonstrated, as various generic AI services were applied to the test data with mixed success.

This, however, reflected the need to train such AI services with lots of data relevant to cultural heritage collections, rather than any inherent shortcomings of the technologies themselves. The proposed framework is widely applicable and does not take the ‘one size fits all’ approach of previous aggregators. In particular, an institution could initially be represented with just collection-level records that would still be useful, adding item-level records and digitised assets as and when they were ready, in whatever form and through whatever means they were able to provide them.

Case study: 3D Digitisation of the British Library’s historic globe collection

In 2019 the British Library embarked upon an ambitious project to unlock one of its most beautiful yet technically challenging collections.

Historic globes form a small but unique subset of the UK’s national collection of 4 million maps. Ranging in date from 1600 to 1900 and in size from an inch to a metre in diameter, these terrestrial and celestial spheres provide crucial insights into the history of science and society, and in particular the development of the

⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/mapping-digitised-collections-in-england>

British mapmaking industry. However, because of their format, age, precision craftsmanship and materials, these objects pose particular challenges for handling and interpretation.

'Globes 3D' brings these objects to a wider online audience whilst preserving them for future generations. Utilising the British Library's in-house multi-camera 3D imaging system, the complete surface areas of 30 globes were photographed using focus stacking.

Working alongside the digitisation company Cyreal, Library technicians were then able to construct 3D digital models showing historical geospatial data to sub-millimetre accuracy using photogrammetry.

These 3D digital models of the globes are now available on the Library's main website (<https://www.bl.uk/collection-guides/globes>) via Sketchfab, where anyone online will be able to access and interact with them for the first time and a variety of previously illegible surface features can be read, some with the assistance of multi-spectral imaging.

Alongside the obvious benefits of enabling the Library to preserve the precious original items, the project has generated high-quality interactive content at no cost to the public purse, enabling the library to fulfil its role of facilitating research and enjoyment of the nation's cartographic heritage.

This digital innovation will generate further benefits to the Library in terms of licensing agreements, and for use in displays, exhibitions, loans and partnerships, cultural activities, and in leading learning workshops and education programmes exploring the history of maps, science and society.

Yet digitisation on its own is not enough. Digitised collections need to take account of both human and machine access, ideally following the FAIR data principles to be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. In addition, user research, and communications, access and inclusion strategies all need to be deployed in order to achieve the desired impact.

In some instances, the aim may be to provide a new channel for an existing audience. The Natural History Museum's Digital Collections Programme, for example, aims to support the global audience of scientific researchers. However the aim is not to replicate existing access online, but to increase access by removing physical and cost barriers, and also to transform what research is possible and how, for example, by enabling big data modelling approaches in addition to visits.

Case study: The Natural History Museum Data Portal

Map of digitised specimens from NHM data portal © The Trustees of the Natural History Museum.

Since 2015, the Natural History Museum London has made its research and collections data available through its Data Portal.⁶ This includes specimens digitised through the Museum's Digital Collections Programme, which in many cases are now available on the portal within a day or two of imaging.

As of June 2020, more than 27 billion records have been downloaded from the portal and aggregators in over 400k download events since 2015. The portal contains over 4.8 million records from the specimen collection and over 6 million further records from other research datasets including 3D scans, images, video and audio recordings as well as other structured data in tables. More than 1,000 scientific publications have cited data from the Data Portal, either directly or through aggregators such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), showing the power of joining up collections data and observations of nature globally, and there are many more citations that it is currently not possible to track.

Planned portal functionality will increase data linkage making it easier to discover data associated with our collections. For example, integration with the ORCID system for researcher identification⁷, and increased use of links from specimens to genetic sequence data and 3D resources, enabling users to find related datasets associated with the specimens they are viewing.

⁶ <https://data.nhm.ac.uk>

⁷ <https://orcid.org>

There are many aspects to successful interoperability, and these have implications for the kinds of skills and resources needed to implement them. These include adoption of common schemas (mostly applicable to metadata); common open Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), for example, the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF); common vocabularies (to categorise content consistently); and adoption of a legal framework that makes this possible e.g., non-restrictive licensing or terms.

Case study: Presenting digitised manuscripts from German-speaking lands

Search digitized items...

Institution ^

- Bodleian Libraries (3)
- Dombibliothek Hildesheim (2)
- Herzog August Bibliothek (1)

Religious house ^

- Medingen, Cistercian Nunn... (6)

Language ^

- Latin (6)
- German (4)

Century ^

- 15th century (4)
- 14th century (1)
- 16th century (1)

Decoration ^

- Initials (6)
- Miniatures (4)

J 29

J 27

MS. Don. e. 248

MS. Lat. liturg. e. 18

MS. Lat. liturg. f. 4

1297 Helmst.

Search results from the project website showing six manuscripts once held in the library of the Cistercian Nunnery in Medingen.

The International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) is a global partnership of libraries, archives, museums, and cultural heritage organizations that seeks to promote open standards for access to digital media. The IIIF publishes technical specifications that define how institutions can make their digital image collections interoperable and re-useable (<https://iiif.io>).

The inclusion of audio and video content in the upcoming version will make IIIF the pre-eminent specification for sharing of cultural heritage media. At the Bodleian Libraries in Oxford, IIIF services are a central part of its strategy to increase access to the collections and promote greater discovery and engagement, by making digitized content accessible to users as data that can be re-mixed, re-used, and integrated into their own research.

For example, from 2019 to 2021, the Bodleian and the Herzog August Bibliothek (HAB) in Wolfenbüttel, Germany collaborated to digitize over six hundred manuscripts from their collections. The project sought to virtually 're-unite' items from the collections of former religious houses (convents and monasteries) from

central Germany whose medieval libraries had been dispersed through war and dissolution. The resulting project website uses IIF to present the digitised manuscripts from each institution, where each institution makes available the data for the manuscripts over the IIF APIs and they are presented to the user as a collection that can be searched and browsed within a single interface.⁸

This approach has allowed the institutions to build a thematically unified international collaborative project, while simultaneously ensuring that the digital images and metadata are maintained in well-supported digital collections infrastructure for long-term curation and preservation. Adopting this approach removes the need for large numbers of images to be sent to a centralized project-specific systems for presentation, lengthy website set-up, and even lengthier and complex maintenance of project-specific digital resources to ensure long-term project sustainability. Even though the German Manuscripts digitization project has ended, the digitized materials, and cataloguing and description effort, will continue to live on in well-supported institutional digital collections systems.

The use of IIF has allowed collaborating institutions to reap the benefits of a shared platform for presenting engaging, thematic content for the duration of the project, while also providing for the long-term sustainability of the outputs of the projects and their integration into the larger collections of the individual institutions.

For both object data and metadata, new technologies to automatically create or enhance data such as Optical Character Recognition (OCR), handwriting recognition, Artificial Intelligence (AI) or machine learning could transform the speed and cost at which data can be extracted, enhanced, and discovered; for example by creating natural language descriptions of objects.

At present, however, these technologies are often designed to work best with more standardised material than is typical in collections; so further research and development is required. One can imagine a time where a user might be able to interact with a collection of specimens, photos, sound, and archival documents through one search. The Taskforce welcomes the programme of research projects from *Towards a National Collection*⁹, and the work of the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Infrastructure Roadmap.

⁸ <https://hab.bodleian.ox.ac.uk>

⁹ <https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk>

This Roadmap, *Opportunities to grow our capability*, was published in November 2019, having been requested by the government as a strategic guide to inform investment decisions for the next generation of infrastructure. The theme ‘maintaining and preserving cultural heritage’ has a sub-theme on ‘digitisation and interoperability’ that is highly relevant to this report. Indicative actions include:

- National aggregator for existing collections
- Phased cataloguing, digitisation and connecting of national collections
- Creation of a digital archive for the second half of the twentieth century
- Understanding the heritage of empire and colonialism
- Video and sound search facility

Moreover, while correctly calling for better storage, conservation and access facilities for physical collections, the roadmap also notes that “phased creation of a distributed network of advanced physical and digital facilities would transform access to and search and discovery capability for national collections”.¹⁰

One key route to achieve access and interoperability is already in existence: aggregators. These portals, for example, The National Archives’ Discovery; Jisc’s Archives Hub; and Art UK, are all online sites where different collections can be ‘discovered’ in one place, enabling researchers to find material across organisations, and smaller institutions to benefit from the scale and resource of larger platforms and established audiences. Aggregators also exist for more specialised access such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility which combines natural science collections data with biodiversity observation data.

The Taskforce concluded that, rather than one huge system, transformation for the collections sector will come from *linking data*. Any approaches need to be scalable in order not to leave small institutions behind. Search engine indexing and optimisation are also important to collections discovery.

The Taskforce also noted the conclusions of the report, ‘Mapping Digitised Collections in England’.¹¹ This report described a feasibility study, “to develop and evaluate a practical framework for collecting relevant data in order to map cultural collections and consider what functionalities a tool based on this framework might possess”. The work, led by Collections Trust concluded:

- The test data demonstrated that, with a suitable user interface, the proposed framework would allow end users a single point of access to data at multiple levels from a wide range of institutions.

¹⁰ <https://www.ukri.org/publications/ukri-infrastructure-opportunity-report>, p.84

¹¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/mapping-digitised-collections-in-england>

- The test demonstrated that the prototype could ingest data from a range of institutions using various technical means, and without the institutions having to format their contributions to any kind of set template.
- Although museums, libraries and archives follow different cataloguing standards (often even within the same institution), the flexible nature of the prototype means there is no technical reason why data from all three could not be harvested by an aggregator built using the same architecture, allowing searches to be made across the different collection types.¹²

Licensing, Intellectual Property, copyright and information management (including GDPR) were all issues mentioned by many survey respondents, that again impact publication of and access to digital collections. There is often a key tension for those holding collections between their duty or mission to make collections available, and the need to raise funding by, for example, charging for image rights. Different collection types raise very different issues. For example, copyright is less relevant in relation to natural specimens, but there may be sensitivities about geographic data, for example, in disclosing the location of endangered species.

Use of Creative Commons machine-readable licensing can support interoperability, but may not be suitable, or not well understood, across the sector. There can also be significant issues of perception around the balance of risks between extending the reach of collections data, and loss of curatorial control and informed interpretation. This was an area of work being taken forward elsewhere in the Culture is Digital project – for example, The Space produced a Digital Rights Toolkit.¹³ However, the Taskforce is aware of the need for any work on digitisation to factor in these challenges.

Case study: Art UK

Photography of 'Plaits or Madonna' at the William Lamb Studio in Montrose. Photo credit: Iain Irving.

At least 80% of the UK's national art collection is not on view and the majority has not been photographed. Art UK, the art education charity and online home for every public art collection in the UK, has undertaken two major UK-wide digitisation programmes. First, it digitised all oil paintings in

¹² <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/mapping-digitised-collections-in-england>, p.2-3

¹³ <https://www.thespace.org/resource/the-spaces-digital-rights-toolkit>

public ownership and then digitised sculptures, both within collections and outdoors.

In both programmes a network of researchers ('coordinators') worked alongside freelance art photographers – on a county-by-county basis for paintings and across 25 regions for sculpture. Key tombstone data was imported from collections on spreadsheets, most of which needed processing by coordinators and Art UK's editorial team. For smaller collections, coordinators often entered data themselves. A style guide ensured consistency and artists were 'linked' to ensure unique artist records.

Typically 20MB+ photographs were taken and then imported and linked to data records. For the oil paintings, some 90% of the 212,000 objects were photographed by Art UK with the remainder provided by collections. For this project, photographers visited 3,200 UK venues of which 46% had ten or fewer paintings. For the indoor sculpture digitisation project, data records were imported for every object and 36% photographed by professional photographers, most with multiple angles. Outdoors, all public sculptures were photographed by volunteer photographers trained by Art UK, with over 500 volunteers involved.

Image reproduction agreements now cover the 3,400 venues on Art UK. Venues include museums, universities, hospitals, historic houses within the likes of the National Trust, libraries and other civic buildings. There are currently 54,000 artists represented on Art UK with 57% in copyright. Art UK's copyright team works to trace, record due diligence and gain consent from rights holders with an insurance policy covering orphan works.

The artwork database and images are stored in Art UK's cloud infrastructure, built on top of AWS. This includes layers to manage long-term image preservation. Tags added by the public and machine learning support searching by subject matter. The Art UK website is rich in story content (almost 2,000 articles), learning resources, public engagement opportunities, maps, onward links and shopping opportunities¹⁴. In the last 12 months 5 million unique users visited the site with over 50% from overseas.

Art UK's initiative means that the researchers have access to artworks in the national collection that they would not otherwise have been able to see. In Art UK's November 2022 collection survey, 76% of small collections, 46% of medium collections and 41% of large collections said they only showed their art on Art UK

¹⁴ <https://artuk.org>

(and 14% of very large collections).

Subject to funding, Art UK's next digitisation programme will be outdoor murals. But in future the vast majority of artworks added to the site will come through automated ingest from the Museum Data Service.¹⁵

Recommendations

Recommendation 3:

Nationally-funded programmes focused on interoperability and data-sharing in the cultural and heritage sector, such as The Arts and Humanities Research Council's *Towards a National Collection*, should take account of this report and its recommendations.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to work with UK Research and Innovation, The Arts & Humanities Research Council and others, sharing the work of the Taskforce and inviting collaboration and support.

Recommendation 4:

There should be increased investment, publicity and support for sector-approved content aggregators

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to support national, international and sector specific content aggregators that act as major gateways to digitised collections, such as Discovery, Archives Hub, Art UK and the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, promoting them to their communities.

¹⁵ <https://artuk.org/discover/stories/millions-of-records-from-uk-collections-to-be-unlocked-by-new-museum-data-service>

Theme 3: Standards

Use of appropriate standards, formats and identifiers is key to achieving discoverability, access and impact. It was clear from our survey responses that institutions who set out to digitise parts of their collection, unsurprisingly, tend to use the most appropriate format for the material they are digitising. Using standard formats also supports digital preservation. The Taskforce recommends that International Image Interoperability Framework and identifiers be encouraged in order to facilitate interoperability.

Data quality is a concern. In historic cultural collections of all kinds, data about objects may be inadequate, incomplete or non-existent. When applying standards to transcribing or capturing fields of data, there need to be ways to distinguish consistently, for example, between data that is missing and that is redacted, for example, because of The General Data Protection Regulation. Metadata indicators or descriptions of quality or provenance may be helpful. Systematic sharing of best practice would help here, including use of data fields, quality assurance processes including those for images, and workflows to minimise human error.

While the taskforce remit placed emphasis on examining or developing common standards, in practice there was neither need nor desire for new standards. It was felt that there are already effective standards in place as well as organisations who manage and promote them. The key issue is to improve the extent to which they are used and understood, as well as ensuring that the UK collections sector is well represented in the continuous (and often international) efforts to improve these standards.

For example, in May 2019 the National Conservation Service (NCS) launched a new Quality Mark for Trusted Digitisation Providers to support heritage institutions using third-party digitisation providers and for suppliers to demonstrate their services have been assessed and accredited in relation to designated requirements around the protection of collections.¹⁶

¹⁶ <http://www.ncs.org.uk/ncsqqualitymark.php>

Case study: Sharing Natural History Museum collections data

Map showing the 1.88 billion data points made available through GBIF, the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, thanks to the international development and adoption of the Darwin Core data standard.

Understanding global patterns of biodiversity requires a standardised view of the data from natural history collections and observations across the globe. These data derive from a myriad of sources stored in various formats on many distinct hardware and software platforms.

The Natural History Museum, alongside members of the wider international community, are members of the Taxonomic Databases Working Group, who developed the Darwin Core standard to facilitate the publishing and integration of biodiversity information. This standard, deriving from previous standards work (e.g., Dublin Core), describes core sets of characteristics of biodiversity, which are applicable in many biological domains. The terms are organised into categories covering broad aspects (e.g., event, location, geological context, occurrence, taxon, and identification) of the biodiversity domain or relationships to other resources (e.g., measurements and generic information).

Darwin Core's development spans more than a decade and is flexible enough to accommodate a variety of ever evolving technical contexts in which it might be used. The standard has to be adaptable to accommodate growth (new terms, additional meanings) and interoperability (connections to related information). This is partly achieved through the use of formal "extensions" providing additional terms describing a complementary, related domain information. While the standard has limitations, it has enabled the exchange of almost 2 billion records from 60 thousand datasets across the globe, and underpins tens of thousands of scientific papers that require knowledge on the past and present distributions of species.

Case study: Use of standards and systems to support cross-collections search

Digital Collections team members preparing catalogue data and images for online publication © Ashmolean Museum, University of Oxford.

The Ashmolean 'Digital Collections Programme' has been dedicated to making the museum's collections available online since 2015. Following a hub-and-spoke model, a central team containing both technical and collections expertise have initiated a range of cross-functional activity focussed on the development and maintenance of digital collections content and associated systems and processes at the museum.

While projects often require very specific solutions, the standardisation of particular elements across the programme guarantee cross-searchability and interoperability once collections are published for research, teaching and discovery online.

The implementation of a grading system of bronze, silver and gold for digital collection records provides a pragmatic approach to ensuring both inventory requirements for collections management as well as cataloguing and photography requirements for research and public engagement are met. It also provides a method to quickly identify problem areas and their solution, allocate and prioritise resource, track progress, and support accountability and advocacy of digitisation activity at institutional level.

The associated Data Validation System was built from a specification based on the museum's data and image standards coupled with industry benchmarking and institutional learning from previous digital collection projects. This system has facilitated automation of both data analysis and wrangling so that digital records can meet institutional and sector standards. Collection records identified as reaching bronze, silver or gold level are then drawn from internal systems for publication to the 'Collections Online' website.

The museum's parallel implementation of a central Digital Asset Management system and migration to a new Collections Management System, alongside the introduction of new publication, licensing, and preservation policies and processes – which are projects being run in collaboration with the University's 'GLAM Digital Strategy Programme' – aims to provide a robust infrastructure for the sharing and linking of our digitised collections content.

Over two hundred thousand records from across the museum's diverse collections have thus far been prepared and published online on the Ashmolean's current Collections Online platform¹⁷. The systems and standards that underpin this digitisation activity will ensure sustainability and scalability as well as a certain level of data integrity to provide reliable and representative search results that can enable a global audience to discover our world-class collections.

Recommendations

Recommendation 5:

There should be improved dissemination of standards through the provision of a Digital Resources Portal, and knowledge sharing via the Digital Centres of Excellence.

The Collections Digitisation Network will continue to contribute to the development of approaches on persistent identifiers, for example the project undertaken by the Towards a National Collection programme.

¹⁷ <https://www.ashmolean.org/collections-online>

Theme 4: Funding digitisation

Skull of Toxodon platensis collected by Darwin on the voyage of the Beagle (part of an externally funded 3D scanning project at NHM) © The Trustees of the Natural History Museum.

Currently, opportunities for securing funding for digitisation are limited and, in some areas, reducing. In addition, many organisations struggle to identify sources of funding, or, once identified, to make successful business cases based on evidence of impact. The Taskforce identified the need to create new opportunities, give advice on unlocking new funding, and maximising the funding that currently exists.

The Taskforce survey showed that institutions have received digitisation funding from multiple sources, including in-house, research funding, specific digitisation grants, commercial partnerships and philanthropic funding. The majority of digitisation is funded in-house, with relatively few cultural institutions entering into commercial partnerships, so there are opportunities here to increase partnership, philanthropic sponsorship and a variety of economic models.

Collections content has value, but the Taskforce recognised the lack of established methodologies for expressing that value – for example neither collections nor research based on them have systematic methods for economic valuation; and economic models for cultural value are still relatively novel and often contested.

Case study: Testing new business models for collaborative digitisation

Over the years, Jisc has played a fundamental role in supporting digitisation of archives and special collections to foster innovative research, teaching and learning within the Higher Education (HE) but also heritage sector. In recent years Jisc has been testing alternative business models for a more strategic, coordinated and sustainable approach to digitisation.

Its 'Social Movements of the 20th Century' project is based on a variation of a 'library crowdfunding' model of joint funding between 13 universities and Jisc. Institutions purchased early access to Reveal Digital's 'Independent Voices' collection, which was also created through a programme of 'library crowdfunding' in the US and is now openly available¹⁸. Part of the libraries'

¹⁸ <https://www.jstor.org/site/reveal-digital/independent-voices>

access fees was supplemented by Jisc to fund the digitisation of more UK-based content.

The project tested a new collaborative and financial model and has digitised content from some of the participating libraries, including a collection of women's pamphlets during the inter-war period drawn from the archives of the London School of Economics and records of the National Union of Women Teachers from University College London. The project also worked with Digirati to explore how we can use the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) standard to support metadata enrichment and more efficient digitisation and cataloguing workflows.¹⁹

'Digitising the History of science in Great Britain' is another collaboration Jisc initiated with international publisher Wiley, to increase access to digital collections.²⁰ Jisc and Wiley co-funded the creation of a new digital resource, The British Association for the Advancement of Science—Collections on the History of Science (1830s-1970s) and worked with Jisc HE members to identify material drawn from universities' archives and special collections. The new collection includes nearly 1 million pages of documents from 12 UK university archives and library collection and is delivered through the Wiley platform.

The collaboration is the first to offer universities a chance to influence what material is digitised by a commercial publisher. All Jisc members institutions and affiliates, such as national libraries, have free access to the collection and after ten years from publication, this resource will become open and authentication/password-free globally.

This 'mixed economy' of digitisation funding can be a strength, enabling institutions to spread risk and continue digitisation even if one funding source fails. However it also impacts strategic and sustainable digitisation, leading to a patchwork of short-term projects with uneven coverage, and often a focus on the front end rather than on preservation or on robust data and metadata creation.

There is also a need for advice specifically on assessing digitisation costs and models which need to take into account the very variable costs of digitising different types of collections items. Some items may need a bespoke approach

¹⁹ <https://digitisation.jiscinvolve.org/wp/2019/12/04/changing-digital-workflows-with-iiif-and-semantic-tools-report/>

²⁰ <https://www.jisc.ac.uk/innovation/projects/digitising-the-history-of-science-in-great-britain>

because of size or complexity, while others can follow more standardised mass digitisation workflows.

The survey also highlighted particular challenges for small cultural institutions, who may lack the expertise, track record or resources needed to make funding bids. Making multiple bids on an ongoing basis, which can be necessary for sustainable funding, is resource-intensive. One approach for addressing this on the part of national collections institutions is the Centres of Excellence model set out above, which could build partnerships between institutions large and small with complementary collections or expertise, and could provide not only advice on applications to funding bodies, but also mentoring through the process and a channel for collaborative joint bids.

Crowdfunding is an area that some institutions have used successfully, but relatively little to date to fund digitisation. While the traditional crowdfunding model of exchanging monetary support for tangible 'rewards' may be difficult to envisage for digitisation, some innovative adaptations of this model are emerging. Reveal Digital is a good example of a US-based initiative that uses 'library crowdfunding' to digitise collections and publish them openly based on a cost-recovery open access model. Jisc piloted this model in the UK with 13 University libraries, and are now digitising new content based on a joint-funding approach.

Nesta has also led an arts and heritage matched crowdfunding pilot on the Crowdfunder platform, in which the £251,500 in matched funding provided by Arts Council England and the National Lottery Heritage Fund within the pilot helped leverage an additional £405,941 from a crowd of 4,970 backers.²¹

Another area to explore is digitisation 'on demand' or as a service, whether commercial, at cost, or free to the user (for example, funded by grants). In natural sciences, the EU-funded SYNTHESYS+ project for research access to European collections, led by the Natural History Museum, launched a new fund in 2020 for Virtual Access – effectively to fund digitisation on demand for collections that meet research community needs and support research into sustainability goals. The first round of funded projects includes the digitisation of bat specimens to support future virology research into coronaviruses.

²¹ <https://www.nesta.org.uk/project/arts-and-heritage-matched-crowdfunding-pilot/>

Recommendations

Recommendation 6:

Economic valuation models for collections and collections data should be developed. The Department of Digital, Culture Media and Sport should support further study in this area.

The Collections Digitisation Network will provide case studies and share research to illustrate collections value, impact and best practice.

Theme 5: Supporting skills

Member of NHM digitisation team at work © The Trustees of the Natural History Museum.

The Taskforce survey identified gaps in skills and human resources for best practice digitisation and data mobilisation – this includes a range of skills from curation (knowledge of particular collections types) and digitisation (imaging workflows) to funding cases and understanding best practices in data release.

Without access to these skills, content release is restricted, particularly for smaller institutions. A lack of sustainable funding can also lead to skills loss, poor retention and short-termism. There are therefore opportunities for new models, for example, knowledge centres, training, or a hub and spoke or Centres of Excellence model with larger institutions supporting smaller partners.

Survey respondents felt that they would value a single hub pulling together information about digitisation into one place. They were particularly interested in support with making funding applications, and the implementation of best practice standards. The Taskforce therefore commissioned Collections Trust to create resources relating to digitisation for an existing central online hub of resources. This provides a single point of access to the best resources around funding, standards, digitisation guides and so on. This can be found at Culture24's Digital Pathways resource bank.²² Many of the participants spoke about how knowledge-sharing can build digital maturity over time. Staff in institutions can grow in capability and capacity via learning-by-doing. We need to look at development programmes to support this that include partnering, mentoring, and secondment opportunities alongside traditional skills training schemes.

Recommendations

Recommendation 7:

The digital skills and maturity of the cultural sector should be developed, for example through Art Council England's Digital Culture Network and Digital Maturity Index, and the National Lottery Heritage Fund's Digital Skills for Heritage initiative.

The Collections Digitisation Network will provide mentoring, skills sharing, and workshops, subject to resources.

²² <https://digipathways.co.uk/pathways/what-does-digitising-collections-involve>

Theme 6: Preservation and sustainability

There is little point in creating digitised content and data if there is no strategy to maintain it. Digital preservation enables the longevity of digitised content, yet it has been a poor cousin in the past, with the result that much digitised content is no longer available, either because it has not been preserved or because links to it have been broken. In human terms, use of digitised collections is key, ensuring that an interested audience can give early warning of any risks to access and demand action. In technological terms, however, there is clearly more to be done.

There is also a link between digitisation and physical conservation or preservation. The survey found that many archives and libraries favoured digitising their collection for these purposes. If a collection is digitised and made available, then there can be a reduction in the use of originals. A digital surrogate or snapshot can capture information that would be lost due to gradual or catastrophic degradation of physical objects over time, increasing resilience and enabling disaster recovery.

This is not a straightforward relationship – digitisation can sometimes increase the demand for items by raising the profile of little-known collections; and digital versions are not substitutes for the physical originals, which for example may be required as ‘vouchers’ to verify previous research and analyses, or may be necessary to enable additional research into the object’s materiality. Digital preservation and sustainability, however, are seen as crucial to the longevity of both digital and physical assets. Curation and maintenance of digital assets cost money, but if it is not done, the public will no longer be able to use them. A large amount of funding has been invested by public bodies such as the Heritage Fund over the last 20 years for content digitisation. Further investment in preservation infrastructure ensures that this initial investment is worthwhile.

This was an area where the sector has a tangible sense of frustration about short-term project funding approaches, and where there is a real appetite for a strategic cross-cutting and long-term approach to infrastructural needs and investments. Public digital funding could achieve significant change by supporting shared and recognised resources. Solutions to address some of these issues could be implemented. For example, exit strategies for projects could include ways in which digital components and assets can be reused; and institutions willing to take in ‘orphaned’ material should also be made known as repositories of last resort.

Case study: Preserving digital data for research and teaching

Polonsky Fellows in action © Bodleian Libraries, University of Oxford.

The Polonsky Digital Preservation Programme was a collaboration between Bodleian Libraries in Oxford and Cambridge University Library (2016-2018), made possible through generous funding from the Polonsky Foundation. The resulting 'Digital Preservation at Oxford and Cambridge' project aimed to enhance the libraries' digital programmes by building on existing expertise and research in the field of digital preservation and curation.

Six digital preservation Fellows were organized as a team of three within each institution, directed by a Project Board, and also worked collectively as a larger team. At each institution the Fellows focused on different aspects of digital preservation identified as key to delivering a successful programme: policy and planning, outreach and staff development, and technical implementation. In the first year of the project the Fellows focused primarily on auditing the libraries' collections of images and research data, resources which had been created since the mid-1990s. A staff survey was also launched to identify skills and knowledge gaps around digital preservation in current job roles.

In the second year the Fellows began looking at the implementation of their recommendations. This included developing policy and strategy, piloting technical solutions, and devising an all-staff training programme. The Fellows also developed a number of business cases, which resulted in additional funding for follow-on digital preservation projects in Oxford University's libraries and museums during 2019-2020.

The Programme resulted in a step change in the approaches of both libraries (and their host institutions) to digital preservation. There is now greater recognition of the central role that libraries must play in the creation and preservation of digital data, and how this work provides a vital underpinning to the teaching and research activities of the wider university.

Case study: BFI Britain on Film

With the growing transition from physical to digital display, the British Film Institute (BFI) recognised within its Film Forever strategy that, without support, the UK's screen heritage was in danger of being stranded in the analogue domain and forever inaccessible to the people of Britain. Aided by National Lottery funding, a five year national programme of works (2012-2017) invested

in preservation from analogue originals to digitisation, interpretation and access. It is potentially one of the largest and most complex archive preservation projects ever undertaken in the UK and is a paradigm shift from analogue to digital for the National Archive.

From inception, BFI broke new ground: created its first ever video-on-demand platform, BFI Player; consulting with commercial facilities, commercial Rights holders and Regional and National Film Archives to establish technical standards for film preservation and access.

Like the award-winning Master Film Store at Gaydon, to keep our master nitrate film safe; the BFI built a state-of-the-art data centre and new Digital Preservation Infrastructure, designed to operate seamlessly with existing systems to keep the digits safe and accessible. This enables processes for ingest, media asset management, long term preservation and access to benefit all BFI born digital and digitised collections.

With our partners, we curated over 10,000 film works for digitisation, regularly released to the public, primarily online. The majority are free-to-watch as part of the landmark Britain on Film and other key themed collections on BFI Player. Public access was extended further through theatrical, broadcast and home entertainment releases on Blu-ray and DVD.

Today we have substantially transformed access to the nation's film heritage with over 90 million video views (and growing) of titles available of Britain on Film. Above all the project has encouraged millions of people to engage with and enjoy their screen heritage for the first time.

Recommendations

Recommendation 8:

Funders such as The Arts and Humanities Research Council and National Heritage Lottery Fund should consider including preservation and sustainability within their requirements.

The Collections Digitisation Network will support the production of guiding principles for digital preservation.

Recommendation 9:

Link existing initiatives to maximise investment and research into sustainable long-term data infrastructure.

The Collections Digitisation Network will collaborate with UK Research and Innovation and The Arts and Humanities Research Council initiatives, such as Infrastructure roadmaps and Towards a National Collection, and new areas of action when these arise.

Conclusion

Digitisation and related data-discovery technologies have the potential to transform access to the depth and breadth of cultural heritage assets that exist across our sector. There is appetite and enthusiasm to develop the UK into an innovative, strategic and dynamic world-leader for digitisation. Other countries have some great examples of good practice and consistent investment. There are opportunities for us to learn from those, and to leapfrog into a leadership position by adopting new drive and a new approach.

There is a huge economic and scientific benefit to this work. Until we digitise, and digitise in a way that enables data to be visible, discoverable and linked, we cannot exploit the extraordinary potential of the riches of the UK's cultural heritage. But that is not all. As well as economic gain, there is social value to our heritage, and the more it is shared, the more that value grows. Digitally enabled local spaces can bring our heritage to new communities via new forms of engagement, stimulating new personal commitment to education and community. And digital collections are crucial for research – put simply, they expand access for researchers, directly improving the breadth and quality of the research.

With programmes such as *Towards a National Collection* and the work on the UK Research and Innovation Infrastructure Roadmap now moving ahead, as well as the new strategy from Arts Council England, this is a perfect time to publish our report and leverage our work.²³ The Digitisation Taskforce (now the Collections Digitisation Network) will continue to act as a knowledge-sharing network, and to work with others to open doors to the extraordinary treasure trove that is the UK's cultural heritage.

²³ <https://www.artscouncil.org.uk/publication/our-strategy-2020-2030>